

Reviewer 3:

Thank you for appreciating our work. We say that we experimented with many functions to decide the ones we will be using based on its properties (domain, range, slope, etc.) and results. We feel we have provided enough reasons for using the `instant_score` and `score` functions (equations 3, 8, 9) as well, however if unclear we can present it in more detail. We need to improve the Coefficient Of Variation (Table 4) and still ensure no server shoots or diminishes its timeout which can result in the elections running forever. Thus, we need to meet the domain and range restrictions that we described in Table 2 and reasoned with the paragraph below equation 4. To suit these requirements we used the functions mentioned (figures 2, 4). For `instant_score`, $\cos(x)$ itself does not suffice the conditions in Table 2 and it's a strictly decreasing function in our domain. To correct the monotonicity and balance curve's slope for better Coefficient Of Variation we multiply the arctan component. These two components do not provide the Coefficient Of Variation in our required range owing to its small slope. To improve this, we multiply $\text{square_root}(2)$. Finally, to satisfy the last condition in Table 2, we add one. The other score functions are constructed similarly. We nowhere claim that the score functions we use are the best, however due to the reasons provided and the results achieved it proficiently suits our needs. Finding the theoretically optimal score functions can be a research topic in itself and fellow researchers are invited to pursue it. Moreover, if needed we can definitely add these details in our camera-ready version.

We hope we have addressed your concerns sufficiently and any upgrades to our score will be really helpful.